

NDAC/LO/002

1982 May 7

ERRATA (1):

Mathematical Formulation of the Scientific Data Analysis
for the Space Astrometry Mission HIPPARCOS
 (Annex A to NDAC Proposal)

Page	Place	Instead of	Read	
5	line 6 f.b. (equation)	(no equation number)	(2.9)	✓
24	line 9	$\tilde{E}'T_{ref}$	$\tilde{E}'\tilde{T}_{ref}$	✓
36	upper right corner	Page 35	Page 36	✓
36	Eq (12.4)	$\sin \delta_r \sin(\alpha_o - \alpha_r)$	$\cos \delta_r \sin(\alpha_o - \alpha_r)$	✓
36	Eq (12.6) (two places!)	- " -	- " -	✓
47	line 10 f.b.	(A.3)	(B.3)	
50	line 4	(A.9)	(B.9)	